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Research Article

Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol Fumarate in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

A straightforward, focused, exact, and high-performance liquid chromatographic reverse phase approach was created for the simultaneous measurement of Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol Fumarate in tablet form. A 55:20:25 v/v/v mobile phase comprising TEA, acetonitrile, and methanol was employed in an isocratic mode Agilent. The effluent was measured at 225 nm, and the flow rate was 1 ml/min. Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol Fumarate had retention times of 3.79 and 9.71 minutes, respectively.

INTRODUCTION

Bisoprolol fumarate Chemically referred to as 1-(propan-2-ylamino)-3-[4-(2-propan-2-yloxyethoxymethyl) phenoxy] propan-2-ol, bisoprolol is a member of the beta blocker class of medications, which is mostly used to treat cardiovascular disorders. With very little effect on β_2 -adrenergic receptors, bisoprolol specifically inhibits β_1 -adrenergic receptors in the heart. Its selectivity for β_1 -adrenergic receptors may be due to the two substituents in the para position of the

benzene ring. Angina pectoris, congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction, and mild to moderate hypertension are all treated with bisoprolol.

Bisoprolol Structure

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Hydrochlorothiazide¹⁵ is a member of the thiazide diuretic medication class. Thiazide diuretics assist prevent the body from retaining fluid by reducing the amount of electrolytes that are reabsorption from the renal tubules. Chemically speaking, 6-chloro-1,1-dioxo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine-7-sulfonamide is the name given to hydrochlorothiazide (Figure 2). Treatments for congestive heart failure, diabetic insipidus, renal tubular acidosis, hypertension, hypoparathyroidism, osteoporosis, and kidney stone prophylaxis sometimes involve the use of hydrochlorothiazide.

HCTZ structure

In addition to treating hypertension, the low-dose combination of bisoprolol and hydrochlorothiazide helps prevent strokes, heart attacks, and kidney issues.⁹⁻¹⁰. When one medication is insufficient to manage blood pressure, this combination is employed. When these two medications are used together, the dosage of each medication can be decreased, lowering the likelihood of adverse effects. The dosage formulations containing bisoprolol and hydrochlorothiazide are becoming a common drug in cardiovascular therapy because of the aforementioned benefits.

RP-HPLC technique using a photodiode array detector for simultaneous quantitative measurement of hydrochlorothiazide and bisoprolol in tablet and bulk dose forms. The process that was established was validated in compliance with ICH recommendations

EXPERIMENTALS

Instrumentation

The Agilent 1260 Infinity was the HPLC apparatus used. Both the chromatographic separation and

quantification were performed using an Agilent 5TC C18 analytical column (250 mm × 4.6 mm), which was maintained at room temperature. The tablet sample, drug standard solutions, and mobile phase were filtered using a Whatman filter paper before being fed into the HPLC apparatus.

Drugs, Chemicals and Reagents

Merck Specialities private limited, located in Aurangabad, India, provided gift samples of the reference standards for hydrochlorothiazide and bisoprolol fumarate. Research Lab Limited (Mumbai, India) provided TEA of HPLC quality. and acetonitrile, Methanol which is provided by Research Lab Limited (Mumbai, India). Water of HPLC grade was used for the entire analysis. Bisobis H tablets were advertised as containing 6.25 mg of hydrochlorothiazide and 2.5 mg of bisoprolol fumarate

Chromatographic conditions

Mobile phase : 0.2% TEA: Acetonitrile: Methanol (55:20:25 v/v/v)

Flow rate : 1mL/min

Detection wavelength : 225 nm

Column temperature : Room temperature

Injection volume : 20 µL

Run time : 12 min

Detector: PDA detector

Standard Drug Solution

Precisely weigh out 10 milligrams of Bisoprolol Fumarate and 25 mg of Hydrochlorothiazide, and then transfer the mixture into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Transfer 40 milliliters of iso-propyl alcohol and 60 milliliters of water (serving as a diluent) into the volumetric flask containing the Bisoprolol Fumarate and Hydrochlorothiazide. To filter the mixture, use filter paper No. 41. Raise the final volume with the water to the mark on the volumetric flask. Transfer 5 milliliters of the previously made solution into a second 100 milliliter volumetric flask using a pipette. The volumetric flask should be filled with water until the designated volume is attained.

Tablet Sample Solution

Weigh each of the ten tablets to find their average weight. Crush the tablets into a fine powder. A 100 ml volumetric flask is filled with the equivalent of 25 mg of Hydrochlorothiazide after the tablet powder has been weighed. Strain the mixture containing the tablet powder through filter paper No. 41 to remove any impurities or solid particles. After the solution was filtered, 5 ml was pipetted out and transferred to another 100 ml volumetric flask. The volumetric flask should be filled with water until the designated volume is attained. When the solution is prepared, introduce it into the HPLC device for analysis.

METHOD VALIDATION

System Suitability

A functional standard solution containing Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol Fumarate was prepared in accordance with protocol, and it was introduced to the HPLC system five times. The system suitability characteristics were evaluated using standard chromatograms, where the percentage RSD of the retention duration, tailing factor, theoretical plates, and peak regions from five replicate injections were computed.

Specificity

The capacity to distinguish the target analyte from other components in the sample is known as specificity. The procedure's specificity was covered by the connection of the chromatograms for the standard, sample, blank, and placebo.

Accuracy

The accuracy of the procedure was measured by applying the traditional addition recovery strategy. Three different concentrations of a standard stock solution containing known amounts of bisoprolol fumarate and hydrochlorothiazide were added to the previously examined sample solutions: 80%, 100%, and 120%. Three examinations of the solutions at each level were conducted while revisiting these alternatives. A percentage of the

recovery was used to determine and report the accuracy.

Precision

The precision of the analytical process is defined as the degree of agreement between multiple measurements obtained from repeated samplings of the same homogenous material under prescribed conditions. Precision can be seen in both system and method implementation.

Linearity and Range

Inject six reference solutions containing hydrochlorothiazide and bisoprolol fumarate to show the assay's linearity. A correlation coefficient of 0.99 was found. A plot of linearity was produced.

Robustness

The inclusion of mobile phases minus and plus is an intentional modification to the procedure. Moreover, the RSD percentage is computed.

Solution Stability

Standard and sample solutions were tested for 24 hours at room temperature to show the stability of the solutions during analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The acceptance requirements are satisfied by the system suitability metrics. Make sure the system is appropriate before beginning any analytical testing, including HPLC analysis.(Table1). The comparison between the chromatogram of the standard solution and the sample solution containing hydrochlorothiazide and bisoprolol fumarate is evident.(Figures 3, 4, and 5) The main peak's retention time is unaffected by the gap.(Tables 2 and 3)

A favorable relationship with a correlation of 0.99 can be established by adjusting the area between the drug and the drug concentration.(Tables 4 and 5) (Figures 6 and 7) Repeated investigations' findings indicated that the cure rate varied from 95% to 103%. The fact that excipients don't obstruct the analyte analysis suggests that this method was chosen (Table

6&7).The method's precision %RSD values are less than 2%, suggesting that it has good precision for the simultaneous analysis of bisoprolol fumarate and hydrochlorothiazide.(Tables 8 and 9) The findings highlight the significance of the approach by proving that minute variations in temperature and composition of the mobile phase have no effect on the drug's peak area.(Tables 10 and 11)

At room temperature, samples and reference solutions remain stable for a whole day.(Tables 12 and 13)

In Conclusion, we can say that the quantitative determination of hydrochlorothiazide and bisoprolol fumarate in formulation using the

approved RP HPLC method is accurate, precise, affordable, and easy to use. The method's conformity with ICH requirements was confirmed. As a result, the technique may be used successfully to the regular examination of tablets containing bisoprolol fumarate and hydrochlorothiazide.

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Conflict of interest

The authors claim they don't have any competing interests.

Table No.1: System suitability for of Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol fumarate

Sr.no	Surface area of Bisoprolol Fumarate	Retention time Bisoprolol Fumarate	Surface area of Hydrochlorothiazide	Retention time Hydrochlorothiazide
1	171.273	9.849	2430.98	3.812
2	168.892	9.809	2510.81	3.811
3	173.333	9.718	2454.21	3.826
4	170.631		2412.42	2412.42
5	167.375		2515.93	2515.92
Average	170.3008		2464.87	
St. dev.	2.27		46.7191	
%RSD	1.33		1.89	

The acceptance requirements are satisfied by the system suitability metrics. Make sure the

system is appropriate before beginning any analytical testing, including HPLC analysis.

Table 2: Specificity data for sample

Name	Area	Retention time
Hydrochlorothiazide	2649.10	3.893
Bisoprolol Fumarate	191.38	10.113

Table 3: Specificity data for standard

Name	Area	Retention time
Hydrochlorothiazide	2603.26	3.758
Bisoprolol Fumarate	181.78	9.735

Table 4: Data sheet for linearity of Hydrochlorothiazide

Concentration Hydrochlorothiazide	Area of Hydrochlorothiazide
0	0
7.5	1450.07
10	2064.63

12.5	2479.38
15	2840.94
17.5	3176.82

Table 5: Data sheet for linearity of Bisoprolol Fumarate

Concentration of Bisoprolol Fumarate	Area of Bisoprolol Fumarate
0	0
3	86.45
4	131.945
5	169.528
6	199.135
7	223.967

Table No 6.: Data sheet for accuracy of Hydrochlorothiazide

% Level	Area	Amount mg added	Mg found	% recovery	Average	SD	RSD
80%	2165.433	21.5	29.96	102.15	102.033	0.46	0.45
	2161.162	21.4	29.91	102.42			
	2001.872	20	20.30	101.52			
100%	2509.896	25	25.45	101.82	102.08	0.29	0.28
	2523.992	25	25.59	102.39			
	2564.901	25.5	26.01	102.01			
120%	2976.429	30	30.18	100.62	100.91	1.83	1.81
	2857.006	29.2	28.97	99.23			
	3194.977	31.5	32.40	102.87			

Table No.7: Data sheet for accuracy of Bisoprolol Fumarate

% Level	Area	Amount mg added	Mg found	% recovery	Average	SD	RSD
80%	142.909	8.2	8.39	102.33	101.24	1.29	1.27
	143.657	8.3	8.43	101.63			
	132.604	7.8	7.78	99.82			
100%	174.056	10.2	10.22	100.20	100.35	0.623	0.621
	169.997	10	9.98	99.82			
	175.514	10.2	10.30	101.04			
120%	205.335	12	12.05	100.47	100.38	1.60	1.59
	201.799	12	11.84	98.74			
	218.749	12.6	12.84	101.94			

Table No8.: Method Precision of Hydrochlorothiazide

Sample no	Area	% Assay
1	2466.81	100.07
2	2469.72	100.19
3	2512.63	101.93
4	2561.93	103.93
5	2480.07	99.21

6	2466.21	99.21
	Average	100.85
	St. dev.	1.76
	%RSD	1.74

Table No.9: Method precision of Bisoprolol Fumarate

Sample no	Area	% Assay
1	172.395	101.229
2	174.001	102.172
3	173.009	101.590
4	169.849	99.734
5	176.453	102.742
6	175.956	102.453
	Average	101.653
	St. dev.	1.09
	%RSD	1.07

Table No.10: Robustness data for Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol fumarate (for flow rate 0.8ml/min)

Sr.no	Area Hydrochlorothiazide	Retention time Hydrochlorothiazide	Area Bisoprolol fumarate	Retention time Bisoprolol fumarate
1	3055.383	4.752	201.246	13.103
2	3071.482	4.865	204.068	13.189
3	2984.5	4.759	199.728	13.117
Average	3037.122		201.68	
Stdev	46.27		2.20	
%RSD	1.52		1.09	

Table No.11: Robustness data for Hydrochlorothiazide and Bisoprolol fumarate (for flow rate 1.2ml/min)

Sr.no	Area Hydrochlorothiazide	Retention time Hydrochlorothiazide	Area Bisoprolol fumarate	Retention time Bisoprolol fumarate
1	2265.364	3.178	155.553	8.796
2	2227.884	3.159	157.669	8.763
3	2297.945	3.172	152.384	8.797
Average	2263.731		155.202	
Stdev	35.05		2.65	
%RSD	1.54		1.71	

Table No.12: Standard Solution Stability data for Hydrochlorothiazide and of Bisoprolol fumarate

Name	Area Hydrochlorothiazide	Relative difference Hydrochlorothiazide	Area Bisoprolol fumarate	Relative difference Bisoprolol fumarate
Standard solution 0hr	2724.71	0.49	196.55	-1.35
Standard solution 24 hr	2738.12		193.89	

Table No.13: Sample Solution Stability data for Hydrochlorothiazide and of Bisoprolol fumarate

Name	Area of Hydrochlorothiazide	Assay of Hydrochlorothiazide	Area of Bisoprolol fumarate	Assay of Bisoprolol fumarate
Sample solution 0 hr	2512.63	101.93	173.01	101.59
Sample solution 24hr	2485.43	100.83	170.20	99.94

Fig.1: chromatogram of standard

Fig.2: chromatogram of tablet sample

Fig.3: Specificity blank chromatogram

Fig.4: specificity standard chromatogram

Fig.5: Specificity sample chromatogram

Fig.6: linearity graph of hydrochlorothiazide

Fig.7: linearity graph of Bisoprolol Fumarate

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